

OIKONYM AS AN OBJECT OF LINGUISTIC STUDY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10030194>

Abstract. *This article discusses onomastics, the object of the study of onomastics. It is concluded that the knowledge of onomastics, oikonyms is formed in the process of cultural and historical formation of civilization. A person selects from the outside world and then fixes in the name only that which interacts with his knowledge of the surrounding reality, reflects his individual view of the world and corresponds to his existential values.*

Keywords: *onomastics, oikonyms, toponyms, proper name, linguistics, ethnonyms, linguistic analysis.*

The names occupy one of the main places in the official languages. Many linguistic studies have been dedicated to them, in which all kinds of views on the essence, structure and features of names have been reflected. Proper names have been the subject of interest of many scientists since ancient times both in the East and in the West, onomastics as a branch of linguistics that studies proper names received the status of science only in the 30s of the XIX century. The object of the study of onomastics is the history of the appearance of the name and the motives of the nomination, their development, in any class of onyms (a set of personal names), transitions of onyms different in form and nature, word-formation, semantic and typological features of the formation of proper names [1].

The term onomastics has several meanings. It denotes the group science of proper names and proper names themselves. Onomastics as a linguistic science is engaged in the study of the meaning of proper names, their multifunctional feature, origin, formation and relationship with absolutely all levels or tiers of language, the theoretical and practical meaning of onomastic science itself, and in addition its relationships with other sciences. Since onomastics appeared at the intersection of sciences, it is distinguished by the extreme complexity of the subject of study. The linguistic component prevails in onomastics, because the information of any name is extracted using linguistic means. Nevertheless, if onomastics were limited only to the linguistic component, there would be no reason to allocate it to a special discipline. Specificity consists in the fact that the subject of linguistics at its core contains ethnographic, historical, geographical, sociological, literary components that can help a linguist identify the specifics of the so-called objects associated with their names.

Onomastics is connected with all spheres of human activity. Wherever selection is required for identification or individualization, a person uses proper names as the most convenient way to highlight an object. Thus, 1) a section of linguistics that studies proper names, the history of their origin and transformation as a result of long-term use in the source language or in connection with borrowing from other communication languages, as well as the patterns of their development and functioning; 2) in a narrower sense, onomastics are proper names of various types (onomastic vocabulary) [2].

Proper name (onym) (tracing paper lat. nomen proprium; onym – from the Greek onoma, onyma – name) is a word, phrase or sentence that serves to distinguish the object named by it from

a number of similar ones, individualizing and identifying this object. Onomastic studies can help to discover migration routes and places of former settlement of different peoples, cultural and linguistic contacts, the most ancient state of languages and the ratio of their dialects) [3].

The study of proper names assumes great importance due to the specific patterns of their transmission and preservation. Because of its social function - to serve as a simple individualizing indication of a specific subject – the proper name is able to retain its main significance with the complete obscuration of its etymological meaning, in this case, with the complete impossibility of associating it with other words of the same language. It follows from this that there is a great stability of proper names that persist not only with revolutionary shifts in the history of a particular language, but also with the absolute replacement of the language of one system by another.

Thus, the possibility is established by etymological explanation of different names to establish the nature of the language in which the corresponding name was formed. Onomastics presupposes an extremely important section of modern linguistics, a complex scientific linguistic discipline equipped with a terminological apparatus, its own range of tasks, the history of research and its own research methods. The nuances of onomastic research are diverse.

The following types are distinguished:

- 1) descriptive onomastics – forms the foundation of onomastic research. This variety provides a general philological analysis and linguistic interpretation of the collected material;
- 2) theoretical onomastics – studies the general patterns of development and functioning of onomastic systems;
- 3) applied onomastics – gives practical recommendations to cartographers, biographers, bibliographers, lawyers. It is connected with the practice of naming, with the functioning of names in live speech and the problems of naming and renaming;
- 4) onomastics of artistic works – is a section of poetics;
- 5) historical onomastics – helps to study the history of the appearance of names, and their reflection in the names of the realities of different eras;
- 6) ethnic onomastics – studies the origin of the names of ethnic groups and their parts in connection with the history of ethnic groups, the ratio of ethnonyms with names of other types, the evolution of ethnonyms, leading to the creation of toponyms, anthroponyms, zoonyms, the connection of ethnonyms with the names of languages (linguonyms) [4].

The study of proper names in literary works and the ways in which they arise should provide important materials for describing different styles and creative methods. But the information for poetic onomastics is not only not developed, but also not selected. Also, multiple expressions of writers and poets about proper names, characterizing the ways of their work in this field, have not been selected (for example, V. Hugo's remarks about names in *Les misérables*, Stern – in *Tristram Shandy*, Leskov – in *Soborians*, entries of proper names – in Chekhov's notebooks) [5]. Modern onomastics is a complex scientific linguistic discipline with its own range of problems and methods.

Onomastic studies can help in the study of migration routes of different ethnic groups, the disclosure of their current habitat, the establishment of the most ancient state of different languages, the definition of linguistic and civilizational contacts of various ethnic groups. Onomastics is a discipline about proper names of absolutely all kinds, about the laws of their formation and functioning. Linguistic onomastics basically includes a geographical, historical, cultural, ethnographic, literary, sociological element that helps to reveal the specifics of named

objects and traditions associated with their names, this takes onomastics beyond the boundaries of linguistics proper and makes it an autonomous discipline that uses mainly linguistic methods. Proper names almost immediately respond to changes in nature and social changes, therefore, proper names can serve as chronologizers of the word, as well as archaeological and historical monuments. Due to the particularly conservative nature of proper names, they survive the time in which they were formed, preserving evidence of the oldest state of the language, and include considerable linguistic and extra-linguistic data that can only be obtained by linguistic methods [6].

Some scientists (O.N. Trubachev, V. Tashitsky) believe that the removal of onomastics beyond the boundaries of linguistics and its separation into a separate discipline using mainly linguistic methods, but closely related to the complex of humanities, as well as the sciences of the Earth and the Universe. Despite the narrow relationship with other humanities, proper names are still the object of the section of linguistics, linguistics – the science of language. This is explained by the fact that any name, any proper name (regardless of which object of living or inanimate nature it refers to) is a word, therefore, it enters the language system, is formed according to the laws of language, lives and is used in speech according to certain laws, undergoes various changes. To this day, an urgent linguistic task is the formation of a toponymic picture of the world, since the toponym has an ethnocultural significance and integrative status, and the toponymic system in a verbalized form reflects the historical, social, linguistic and ethno-cultural features of the ethnos. Onomastic vocabulary reacts sharply and quite actively to socio-political, cultural transformations, fulfilling a special social order of the time in which it is born. To study proper names, historical, etymological, mythological information is attracted. According to researchers, toponymy is a unique subsystem of the language, "part of the cultural environment of the people, their worldview, worldview and world design." The toponymy of any region carries information about significant stages in the history of the culture of the people. "It is important to note that behind almost every onomastic fact there is a historical and living – fictional or quite real – reality, which through various extralinguistic factors creates a specific circle of diverse associations." Of course, the toponym is distinguished by its strict regional affiliation. On the one hand, the geographical name conveys significant information of an extralinguistic nature, and on the other hand, it makes the same information closed to the "uninitiated" who do not possess the necessary background knowledge, which is concentrated in onomastic vocabulary. The figurative nomination contained in the toponym is "always nationally specific in the sense that it consolidates the picture of the world historically formed in the consciousness of the people – the subject of the nomination." Background knowledge is formed in the process of cultural and historical formation of civilization, in connection with which relevant and historical, short-term and long-term toponymic information is distinguished. Toponyms can exist on the map for quite a long time, and even after its disappearance, they remain relevant throughout the history of the people, unlike, for example, ergonyms, whose life is short-lived, and which can be called a "verbal bargaining chip" [7].

Linguistic and cultural analysis of toponyms makes it possible to consider them as a repository of knowledge about the language and culture of the country. Geographical names are considered to reflect the events of the history of the nation, they fix different stages of the formation and prosperity of the language and culture of people [8]. The study of geographical names is one of the important difficulties of modern linguistics, since, arising in various historical periods, toponyms are formed in connection with the peculiarities of the development of society,

reflecting its diverse layers of life. A person selects from the outside world and then fixes in the name only that which interacts with his knowledge of the surrounding reality, reflects his individual view of the world and corresponds to his existential values [9].

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